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DEVELOPMENT AND PROSPECTS OF AN ORGANIC BEEKEEPING HUB IN ONE OF THE POOREST AREAS OF BRAZIL (CASA NOVA, BAHIA)

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14795626

Abstract

This research seeks to understand how a small community of fishing and farmers' families displaced by the construction of a hydroelectric plant, in less than 50 years have converted into honey producers. We used semi-structured interviews in person, recorded, and later transcribed. We collected 22 interviews; 18 have been transcribed and are used here to discuss these results. Originally the families of this community lived by fishing and farming on the banks of the Rio San Francisco. Following the construction of a dam for the construction of a hydroelectric plant in the seventies, lands were offered to the families to re-establish themselves. In this new area for many families there are not yet basic services such as electricity, water, and sewerage. As there is no water available to irrigate crops the families have developed a subsistence economy by raising goats, cows, pigs, chickens, and gardening. They also tried to recover resources from the native forest. One available resource was the honey of the Africanized bees that had recently invaded this area. After a few years, also following training courses and the organization of producer associations, they started beekeeping activities. This activity began to generate considerable profit for the local conditions and so the activity has developed, new people continue to dedicate themselves to this activity and the number of hives continues to increase. Obstacles to this activity continue to be present, as regards management (water shortage, transport difficulties), marketing (currently only through intermediaries), and little aggregate value (despite the product being organic). This research shows that even in an isolated region with a very precarious infrastructure, beekeeping is an economic activity that generates income and cares for the environment. At the same time, it highlights the need for technical assistance activities and research into social technology to develop this activity.

Acknowledgements:

Work supported by FCT through BEESNESS (DOI:10.54499/CIRCNA/BRB/0293/201).